

Invitation to the 2017 “Blind test 5” workshop

The wake behind a yawed wind turbine

L. Sætran^a, F. Mühle^b, J. Bartl^a, J. Schottler^c, M. Hölling^c, M.S. Adaramola^b

^a Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway

^b Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Ås, Norway

^c ForWind, University of Oldenburg, Institute of Physics, Oldenburg, Germany

Contact: lars.satran@ntnu.no, franz.muhe@nmbu.no, jan.bartl@ntnu.no, jannik.schottler@uni-oldenburg.de

Abstract

This is an invitation to a 5th blind test workshop jointly organized by the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), the Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU) and the Carl-von-Ossietzky University of Oldenburg (ForWind).

Modelers are invited to submit predictions for the wake flow behind a yawed turbine for the described test cases and participate in a workshop to be held in **Visby, Gotland, Sweden, prior to the Wake Conference** scheduled for **May 29th, 2017**. In the workshop the results of the computational predictions will be discussed and compared to results of the measurement campaign.

Schedule

- Jan 18th, 2017: Blind test announced on DeepWind conference in Trondheim
- Feb 17th, 2017: Blind test invitation sent out
- May 14th, 2017: Deadline for submission of simulation results
- May 29th, 2017: Blind test workshop prior to the Wake Conference in Visby, Gotland, Sweden

Background

During the last decade, interactions between the single turbines in a wind farm arrangement became a major research focus in the field of wind energy. Accurate prediction tools for the wind farm power production and loadings in various operational states and different atmospheric wind conditions are needed. Analytical wake models manage to describe the wake velocity deficit only qualitatively, while computationally expensive and more complex CFD tools are needed for accurate predictions of the wake flow. Still, these models are dependent on many user-specific input data and require a careful validation with experimentally measured results. Wake flow data measured in full-scale wind farms with met-mast or remote sensing technologies are one option, but are very expensive and difficult to attain due to the complex boundary conditions in the atmosphere. A significantly cheaper option offer down-scaled wind tunnel measurements, in which the boundary conditions are well-controlled. In 2011, a series of blind test workshops initiated by the Norwegian University of Science and Technology was started, comparing wake flow data behind model wind turbines with computational predictions. In the following paragraphs, the test cases of the previous blind test experiments **BT 1-4** are shortly summarized and referenced.

BT1: The first blind test, BT1, was organized in Bergen, in October 2011, and attracted around 40 participants with 11 sets of predictions being submitted. For that blind test, the geometry of a model turbine was made available and the participants were asked to predict its performance and the wake development from the turbine up to 5 rotor diameters downstream. The results are reported by Krogstad and Eriksen [1].

BT2: For the next blind test, held in Trondheim, in October 2012, the test complexity was increased by

adding a downstream turbine behind the upstream turbine. The main task in BT2 was to predict the performance of the downstream turbine, which was affected by the wake developing behind the upstream turbine. The participants were also asked to predict the flow in the wake behind the downstream turbine. Obviously, this was a more complicated test case than BT1 and required more computer resources to be performed properly. Despite this, results were submitted by 9 different participants. The results are reported by Pierella et al. [2].

BT3: For the third blind test, BT3, the complexity was slightly increased again. The same turbines were used, positioned with the same streamwise separation, but shifted slightly sideways so that the wake from the upstream turbine only hit a part of the rotor plane of the downstream turbine. In this way the downstream turbine experienced an asymmetric load. Also, the wake development behind the downstream turbine was no longer axisymmetric. The tests were performed in a virtually turbulence free, uniform flow environment, as well as in a turbulent flow. In the latter case, a grid was installed at the wind tunnel inlet producing a uniform inflow with about 10% turbulence intensity at the location of the upstream turbine. The results from the BT3 are reported by Krogstad et al. [3].

BT4: The focus of the fourth blind test held in Trondheim in October 2015 was the influence of different turbulent inflow conditions on the wake development. Besides a uniform inflow of low turbulence (0.23%) and high turbulence (TI=10.0%), the turbines were exposed to a non-uniform, highly turbulent shear flow (TI=10.1%). The wake was measured behind the upstream model turbine only, while power and thrust results were compared for an aligned setup of two turbines. The wake flow was analyzed up to 8.50 rotor diameters downstream, and performances were compared for different turbine separation distances ranging from 2.77D over 5.18 to 9.00D. Five different computational predictions contributed to the workshop, ranging from Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) to Large Eddy simulations (LES). The results from BT4 are reported by Bartl and Sætran [4].

Motivation for blind test 5

The discussions in the previous blind test workshops revealed a number of interesting technical aspects of wake modelling and resulted in four scientific publications giving insight to the current state of wake modelling. Therefore, it has been decided to invite experts in wake modelling to a fifth blind test experiment focussing on the effects of yaw misalignment.

Wake deflection by an intentional yaw misalignment of single turbines in a wind farm is considered as an effective method for wind farm control. For wind farm operators, the cross-stream deflection in dependence of the upstream turbine’s yaw angle as well as the experienced loads on the upstream and downstream turbine are of great importance. Several studies from the past characterized the wake deflection by 2-dimensional minimum findings in the downstream velocity profiles. On a small model turbine of $D=0.12\text{m}$, Medici and Alfredsson [5] found a wake deflection of about $y/D=0.5$ in the wake $x/D=4$ downstream. On a bigger scaled model turbine of $D=0.90\text{m}$, Krogstad and Adaramola [6] measured a wake deflection of about $y/D=0.2$ diameters in the wake $x/D=1$ diameter, resulting in a similar deflection angle as found by Medici and Alfredsson. Similar results were found in an experimental PIV study by Bastankhah and Porte-Agel [7], who found a deflection of the 2-dimensional wake center of $y/D=0.2$ at $x/D=2$ for a smaller wind turbine model of $D=0.15\text{m}$, although the 2-dimensional wake shape is observed to have a somewhat different shape.

In a recent experimental study Howland et al. [8] investigated the wake behind a yawed drag disc and found that wake trajectory is very dependent on the 2- or 3-dimensional fitting method for finding the wake center. In contrast to earlier publications they also found a curled wake shape for downstream positions from $x/D=5$ and further downstream locations. In computational studies applying LES, Fleming et al. [9] as well as Vollmer et al. [10] found a certain asymmetry in the wake deflection between positive and negative upstream turbine yaw angles. They point out that the wake deflection is very dependent on atmospheric conditions such as turbulence and shear in the inflow. A certain asymmetry in the wake deflection was experimentally confirmed by Schottler et al. [11], who showed an asymmetry in the power production of a downstream turbine depending on the upstream turbine’s yaw angle.

The objective of the presented blind test case is to quantify the ability of different wake modelling

techniques to predict the mean and turbulent wake properties behind a wind turbine operating in yaw. In the first test case this is done for a yawed model turbine exposed to a turbulent shear flow. In a second test case the focus is directed on the power output, thrust and yaw moments that act on a downstream turbine exposed to the wake flow of a yawed upstream turbine. Also, the more complex wake behind this two turbine setup is compared. In a third test case, the impact of the turbine geometry on the wake shape and trajectory is investigated. Therefore, the wake behind a somewhat smaller yawed turbine with different rotor geometry build at ForWind Oldenburg is analysed and compared. This collaborative workshop organized by NTNU, NMBU and the ForWind Oldenburg is thus providing a comprehensive set of yawed test cases, aiming to provide a state-of-the-art description of wake modelling. The results of the workshop are envisaged to be published in a scientific journal after the discussion in the workshop.

1 Definition of the boundary conditions

In this fifth blind test we are focusing on the mean and turbulent wake flow behind a 30° yawed model turbine. We provide wake data for two different inflow conditions (uniform/shear) and two different model turbine geometries. Furthermore, the effect of the wake flow on an aligned downstream turbine is investigated focusing on its power output, thrust force and yaw moment.

In the following we provide detailed information about the setup of the different test cases. Depending on the computational setup, modelers might want to use the exact tunnel dimensions in order to account for possible blockage effects and wall boundary layers. Furthermore, we provide full details of the models' geometry. CAD files which show the exact blade, rotor, nacelle, and tower geometry are available (see Section 1.2). Alternatively, the geometry details can be built from tables containing definitions of the airfoils, and the chord length and twist distributions. All information needed are described in the following sections.

1.1 The wind turbine models

1.1.1 NTNU model wind turbine LARSI

For the purpose of this blind test experiment, a new turbine test rig was constructed at NTNU. A picture of the model turbine called *Laterally Angled Rotating System 1*, abbreviated *LARSI*, is shown in *Figure 1 (a)*. The new test rig features a significantly shorter nacelle and a thinner tower than the test rig used in previous blind test experiments. The shorter nacelle and thinner tower are designed to have a smaller effect on the wake flow. The three bladed rotor has exactly the same geometry and diameter $D_{LARSI} = 0.894m$ as the model turbine *T2* (Sect. 1.1.3), which was utilized in all four previous blind tests. The blades were machined in aluminum and consist of a NREL S826 airfoil section from root to tip (see Sect. 2.1 for airfoil definition).

Figure 1: Model wind turbines (a) NTNU-LARSI (b) NTNU-T2 (c) ForWind

A technical drawing comparing the geometry to NTNU model wind turbine *T2* is presented in *Figure 2*. The nacelle of *LARS1* is no longer circular but rectangular. The individual blades have a total length of $l_{blade}=0.413m$ and are directly mounted on the hub with the diameters $D_{hub,LARS1}=D_{hub,T2}=0.068m$. A detailed technical drawing of the rotor and turbine geometry is attached in *Figure A.1*, Appendix A. The technical drawing indicates the total height of the test rig. However, the hub height of the model wind turbine can be manually adjusted as it is placed on a force balance located underneath the wind tunnel floor.

1.1.2 NTNU model wind turbine *T2*

NTNU’s model turbine *T2*, which is known from all the previous blind tests, is utilized as a downstream turbine in test case 3. It has the exactly same rotor geometry as *LARS1*, although the nacelle and tower shape are different. The nacelle is circular and significantly longer. A picture of *T2* is shown in *Figure 1 (b)*, a scaled technical sketch in *Figure 2 (b)* and detailed technical drawing in *Figure A.2* in the appendix of this document.

T2 and *LARS1* have an almost semi- spherical hub cover at the front. Its deviation from a sphere is small but if the exact geometry is deemed necessary, it may be obtained from the organizers as a table in an Excel file.

1.1.3 ForWind model wind turbine

In order to investigate the effect of the airfoil and turbine geometry on the wake flow one of the model wind turbines of ForWind at the University of Oldenburg was tested at NTNU’s wind tunnel. The turbine has a somewhat smaller rotor $D_{ForWind}=0.580m$ and is based on the SD7003 airfoil (see section 2.2 for further details). A picture of the turbine installed in NTNU’s wind tunnel is shown in *Figure 1 (c)*. In order to lift the hub height of the turbine out of the wind tunnel’s boundary layer, the model was placed on four cylindrical pillars. A scaled sketch of the turbine geometry is shown in *Figure 2 (c)*, while a detailed technical drawing giving all measures is attached in *Figure A.3* in Appendix A.

Figure 2: Scaled sketches of the model turbines (a) NTNU-LARS1 (b) NTNU-T2 (c) ForWind

1.2 Turbine geometry and data sheet download

The CAD files of the turbines' geometries as well as the excel sheets for the data can be downloaded from:

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/ffqqmyciofydq2/AACu3BImUfaQDmq5GRI4KVNea?dl=0>

1.3 Wind tunnel description

The model turbines were tested in the closed-return wind tunnel at the Fluid Mechanics Lab at the Department for Energy and Process Engineering at NTNU in Trondheim. It has a test section which is $2.71m$ wide and $11.15m$ long. The tunnel has a flexible roof, which has been adjusted for zero pressure gradient at $10m/s$. The tunnel heights are given in *Table 1*.

Distance from inlet [<i>m</i>]	Wind Tunnel Height [<i>m</i>]
0.000	1.801
2.810	1.801
5.621	1.813
8.435	1.842
11.150	1.851

Table 1: Wind Tunnel Height of test section as function of distance from the inlet

For test cases 1 and 2 the NTNU turbines *LARS1* and *T2* are installed to have the same rotor axis height above the wind tunnel floor, $h_{hub,LARS1,T2} = 0.890m$, while the ForWind turbine in test case 3 is installed to have a hub height of $h_{hub,ForWind} = 0.820m$ above the wind tunnel floor.

1.4 Inflow conditions

1.4.1 Grid generated shear flow

For this blind test the model turbines are exposed to a grid-generated non-uniform shear flow. The turbulence grid used to create a uniform inflow has a constant mesh size of $m_z=0.240m$ in horizontal direction, while the horizontal bars are arranged with an increasing distance from the floor to the roof of the wind tunnel. The exact positions of the horizontal bars are documented in *Table 2*. The grid has a solidity of about 34% and is built from wooden bars of $47mm \cdot 47mm$ cross-section. *Figure 3* shows the model wind turbines *LARS1* (test case 1), *LARS1* and *T2* (test case 2) and *ForWind* (test case 3) installed in the wind tunnel behind the shear grid.

Figure 3: Model wind turbines (a) LARS1 (test case 1), (b) LARS1 and T2 (test case 2) and (c) ForWind (test case 3) installed behind a shear flow grid

Horizontal bar number	Height of bar center [mm]
8	1600
7	1300
6	1015
5	795
4	575
3	385
2	203
1	40

Table 2: Positions of the horizontal bars of the shear grid (from the wind tunnel floor to the bar center)

1.4.2 Definition of a reference wind speed u_{ref}

The shear in the inflow implies a non-uniform velocity distribution over the rotor area. Therefore, the reference velocity u_{ref} is defined at turbine hub height. An overview of the reference wind speeds and the turbine hub heights is presented in Table 3. The design tip speed ratio λ for all the model turbines is $\lambda_{LARSJ} = \lambda_{T2} = \lambda_{ForWind} = \omega R / u_{ref} = 6.0$.

Test case	Inflow type	Reference speed u_{ref} [m/s]	Turbine hub height h_{hub} [m]	TI at first turbine position [%]
1 (NTNU one turb.)	shear $\alpha=0.11$	10.0	0.890	10.1%
2 (NTNU two turb.)	shear $\alpha=0.11$	10.0	0.890	10.1%
3 (ForWind one turb.)	shear $\alpha=0.11$	7.5	0.820	5.2%

Table 3: Reference wind speed u_{ref} , turbine hub height h_{hub} and turbulence intensity TI for all test cases

As wind shear and turbulence are generated only at the grid position at the tunnel inlet, their development throughout the tunnel is measured for various downstream positions. A common way to describe wind shear is the power law, which expresses the wind speed U as function of height y provided that the wind speed at an arbitrary reference height y_{ref} is known (Eq. 1).

$$\frac{U}{u_{ref}} = \left(\frac{y}{y_{ref}}\right)^\alpha \tag{1}$$

The power law coefficient α describes the strength of shear in the wind profile. The shear grid designed for this blind test experiment creates a profile that can be approximated by shear coefficient of $\alpha=0.11$, which is a realistic coefficient for offshore boundary layers in stable atmospheric conditions [13]. The measured and approximated vertical profiles of the mean velocity and the turbulence intensity at the different downstream positions are presented in Figure 4. Note that the ForWind turbine in test case 3 is located 3D further downstream than the NTNU turbine, resulting in a lower inflow turbulence of TI=5.2%.

Figure 4: Horizontal profiles of (a) mean wind speed and (b) turbulence intensity at all x/D positions

1.4.3 Reynolds number Re_c

The turbines are consistently operated at design tip speed ratio for all test cases in this blind test experiment. The only off design parameter is the turbine yaw angle which is set to $\gamma=30^\circ$. This results in a chord-based Reynolds number of $Re_{c,1,2} \approx \lambda u_{ref} c_{tip}/\nu \approx 1.0 \cdot 10^5$ for the *NTNU* turbines in test cases 1 and 2 respectively $Re_{c,3} \approx 0.7 \cdot 10^5$ for the *ForWind* turbine in test case 3. Herein, c_{tip} is the chord length at the blade tip and ν the kinematic viscosity of air at 20°C.

1.4.4 Turbulence decay and integral length scales L_{uu}

The turbulent kinetic energy in the grid-generated inflow decays with the distance from the grid as shown in *Figure 4 (b)*. Initially, there are significant variations in the flow, but by the time the flow reaches the position of the model turbine the mean velocity matches with the power law within $\pm 1.0\%$. Similarly, the spanwise variation of the turbulence intensity is measured to be constant to within $\pm 1.5\%$. The turbulence intensity in the inflow is defined as

$$TI = \frac{u'}{u_{ref}} . \quad (2)$$

The relation of the dissipation rate of the turbulent kinetic energy E to the streamwise velocity fluctuation u' and the streamwise integral length scale L_{uu} is given by

$$E = \frac{3}{2} A \frac{u'^3}{L_{uu}} . \quad (3)$$

Assuming $A \approx 1$ (taken from Krogstad and Davidson [14]) the integral length in the streamwise direction L_{uu} at the test section inlet was calculated from measurements of u and E for the two inlet conditions.

Downstream position x/D_{LARS1}	Shear inflow	
	TI [%]	L_{uu} [m]
0	10.1	0.097
3	5.2	0.167
6	4.1	0.271

Table 4: Turbulence intensity TI and Integral length scales L_{uu} measured in the empty wind tunnel at different downstream positions

2 Airfoil definition and blade geometry

2.1 NTNU blade: NREL S826 airfoil

The definitions of the NREL S826 airfoil used for the *NTNU* blade can be found in Somers [12] and the airfoil is shown in *Figure 9*. *Table B.1* as shown in Appendix B contains a list of the normalized coordinates for the airfoil. In Somers [12] the lift and drag coefficients are presented for a range of operating Reynolds numbers ($Re_{C_{tip,FS}}=10^6$) for a full scale turbine, which are one order of magnitude higher than the Reynolds numbers prevailing in this model experiment ($Re_{C_{tip,model}}=10^5$).

Figure 9: Shape of the NREL S628 airfoil

Table C.1 in Appendix C defines the airfoil chord length and twist angle as function of the radius for the *NTNU* blade used on turbines *LARS1* and *T2*. All blade elements are based on the NREL S826 airfoil. Herein, the twist angle is measured with respect to the rotor plane. Please note that for the first three blade elements the geometry consists of a circular cylinder used to fix the blade to the hub. Therefore, a major part of this section is located inside the hub when defining the rotor geometry. This section has been identified in the table by setting the twist angle to 120° . Between the last circular section and the first NREL S826 airfoil element, a linear transition is used for a smooth change of shape.

In order to reduce the uncertainty of different airfoil coefficients a standard set of lift and drag coefficients is presented here. The data is calculated in XFOil [15] and the resulting coefficients documented in *Table D.1* attached in Appendix D. Note that this set is given for one Reynolds number only ($Re_c=1.00 \cdot 10^5$). This corresponds to the Re_c obtained at the blade tip at the design operating condition, i.e. at a tip speed ratio of 6.0. Obviously, this will be somewhat incorrect for the inner part of the blade, but the effects on the performance data at the design condition are estimated to be small.

Figure 10: Comparison of C_L/C_D datasets [15, 16]

Furthermore, a number of experimental investigations on a two-dimensional wing section based on the S826 were conducted specifically for low Reynolds numbers. These data also can be used for this blind

test experiment. Sarmast and Mikkelsen [16] performed an experiment on a S826 wing section of the chord length $c_L=0.10m$ at DTU in Denmark. Another experimental set of S826 airfoil data is presented by Ostovan et al. [17] from METU in Turkey. They investigated lift and drag coefficients from $Re_c=7.15\cdot 10^4$ to $Re_c=1.45\cdot 10^5$ on a 2D wing with a chord length of $c_L=0.20m$. A third experimental set of airfoil characteristics from $Re_c=7.00\cdot 10^4$ to $Re_c=6.00\cdot 10^5$ has been measured at NTNU on a wing section of $c_L=0.45m$ at NTNU, Norway. The full NTNU data set is not yet published, but available on request to by the authors of this document. Numerical simulations by Sagmo et al. [18] utilized the experimental NTNU results at $Re_c=1.00\cdot 10^5$ for comparison, and therefore also serve as a good reference.

In *Figure 10* the data from these three experiments are compared to XFOil data as tabulated in *Table D.1*. A good agreement of the datasets is observed in the linear region of the lift curve. Significant differences are seen in the pre-stall and stall region, in which the NTNU measurements result in significantly higher lift coefficients. The XFOil data in *Table D.1* are seen to fall between the measurements, capturing the trends from the METU at the normal operating modes and being right in between NTNU and DTU/METU data at extremely high angles of attack. Therefore, the XFOil data are deemed to be a good average between the experimental datasets.

2.2. ForWind blade: SD7003 airfoil

The definitions of the SD7003-085-88 airfoil used for the *ForWind* blade can be found in Selig et al. [19]. The profile of the airfoil is shown in *Figure 11*. *Table B.2* as shown in Appendix B contains a list of the normalized coordinates for the airfoil. The SD7003-085-88 airfoil is specifically designed for the operation at low Reynolds numbers [19].

Figure 11: Shape of the SD7003-085-88 airfoil

The chord length and twist angle of the *ForWind* blade are presented in *Table C.2* in Appendix C as function of the blade radius. As for the NTNU blade the twist angle is measured with respect to the rotor plane.

Figure 12: Comparison of C_L/C_D of the SD7003 datasets from XFOil and Selig et al [19]

A standard set of lift and drag coefficients for all prevailing Reynolds numbers is presented here. The data is calculated in XFOIL [15] and the resulting coefficients for $Re_c = 1.0 \cdot 10^5$ are documented in *Table D.3* attached in Appendix D. As the turbine is mostly operated below $Re_c = 1.0 \cdot 10^5$ another set of lift and drag coefficients for $Re_c = 0.5 \cdot 10^5$ is presented in *Table D.2*. *Figure 12* compares the lift over drag ratio from XFOIL with experimental data from Selig et al. [19] at two Reynolds numbers. The differences between the experimental data at $Re_c = 1.02 \cdot 10^5$ and $Re_c = 0.64 \cdot 10^5$ are observed to be small compared to the standard dataset from XFOIL at $Re_c = 1.0 \cdot 10^5$. The XFOIL dataset at $Re_c = 0.5 \cdot 10^5$ shows a slightly lower lift values, both compared to the experimental data and XFOIL data from $Re_c = 1.0 \cdot 10^5$.

3 Definition of test cases

For this blind test workshop three test cases are available. It is possible to simulate only one or two of the test cases, if the amount of work or CPU hours sets a limit. This section describes all required details of operating conditions. The blade pitch angle is set to $\beta = 0^\circ$ for all test cases. The density of air can be assumed to be $\rho = 1.20 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

3.1 Test case 1: LARSI turbine exposed to shear inflow

In test case 1 we analyze the wake flow 3D and 6D behind NTNU model turbine *LARSI*. A top view of the setup for test case 1 is sketched in *Figure 12*. The model turbine is located $x=2.0D$ from the test section inlet and is exposed to a shear inflow of $TI=10.1\%$ measured at the rotor location. The characteristics of the shear flow are documented in *Section 1.4*. The turbine’s hub height is adjusted to $h_{hub}=0.890m$. The inflow speed to the test section is set to $u_{ref}=10.0m/s$. The turbine is operated at its design tip speed ratio $\lambda_{T1}=6.0$ and is turned to a yaw angle of $\gamma_{T1}=30^\circ$. For the definition of the yaw angle, it is referred to the *Figure 13*. All parameters for test case 1 are summarized in *Table 5*.

Specifications of test case 1	
Turbine	NTNU <i>LARSI</i>
Rotor location from inlet	$x=1788mm (2.0D)$
Inflow	Shear ($\alpha=0.11, TI=10.1\%$)
Turbine hub height	$h_{hub}=0.890m$
Reference inflow speed	$u_{ref}=10.0m/s$
Tip speed ratio	$\lambda_{T1}=6.0$
Turbine yaw angle	$\gamma_{T1}=30^\circ$

Table 5: Summary of all specifications for test case 1

Figure 13: Top view of the setup for test case 1

3.2 Test case 2: Two aligned turbines exposed to shear inflow

In test case 2 we investigate the effects of upstream turbine yaw on power output, thrust forces and yaw moments of a downstream turbine. Therefore, NTNU turbine *T2* is set up $x/D=3$ rotor diameters downstream of the upstream turbine *LARS1*. The two turbines are perfectly aligned with respect to the rotor center. The power, thrust and yaw moments are measured on turbine *T2*. The wake flow is measured another $x/D=3$ rotor diameters downstream of the second non-yawed turbine. A top view of the setup for test case 2 is sketched in *Figure 14*. All parameters for test case 2 are summarized in *Table 6*.

Specifications of test case 2	
Upstream turbine	NTNU <i>LARS1</i>
Downstream turbine	NTNU <i>T2</i>
Rotor location from inlet <i>LARS1</i>	$x=1788\text{mm}$ ($2.0D$)
Turbine separation distance	$\Delta x=2682\text{mm}$ ($3.0D$)
Inflow	Shear ($\alpha=0.11$, $TI=10.1\%$)
Turbine hub height <i>LARS1</i>	$h_{hub,LARS1}=0.890\text{m}$
Turbine hub height <i>T2</i>	$h_{hub,T2}=0.890\text{m}$
Reference inflow speed	$u_{ref}=10.0\text{m/s}$
Tip speed ratio <i>LARS1</i>	$\lambda_{LARS1}=6.0$
Turbine yaw angle <i>LARS1</i>	$\gamma_{LARS1}=30^\circ$
Tip speed ratio <i>T2</i>	$\lambda_{T2}=5.0$
Turbine yaw angle <i>T2</i>	$\gamma_{T2}=0^\circ$

Table 6: Summary of all specifications for test case 3

Figure 14: Top view of the setup for test case 2

3.3 Test case 3: *ForWind* turbine exposed to shear inflow

In test case 3 the wake flow at 3D and 6D behind the *ForWind* turbine is investigated, exposed to shear inflow. Compared to test case 1, the turbine geometry and the streamwise position of the turbine in the wind tunnel differ. Also the turbine hub height is insignificantly reduced to $h_{hub}=0.820m$. Due to the good performance of the SD7003-085-88 airfoil at low Reynolds numbers the inflow wind speed is reduced to $u_{ref}=7.50m/s$ for this test case. A top view of the setup is sketched in *Figure 15*. All parameters for test case 3 are summarized in *Table 7*.

Specifications of test case 3	
Turbine	ForWind
Rotor location from inlet	$x=4470mm (5.0D_{LARS1})$
Inflow	Shear ($\alpha=0.11, TI=5.2\%$)
Turbine hub height	$h_{hub}=0.820m$
Reference inflow speed	$u_{ref}=7.50m/s$
Tip speed ratio	$\lambda_{TI}=6.0$
Turbine yaw angle	$\gamma_{TI}=30^\circ$

Table 7: Summary of all specifications for test case 3

Figure 15: Top view of the setup for test case 3

4 Required computational data

The main objective of this blind test is to find out how well the wake flow behind a single yawed turbine as well as an aligned turbine array is predicted. A data template in the form of an Excel sheet is provided with the geometry downloads to ensure that the data received from all participants can be presented consistently.

The participants are kindly requested to provide the following output:

Test cases 1 and 3

1. The **power coefficient** $C_P = 2P/\rho u_{ref}^3 A$, the **thrust coefficient** $C_T = 2T/\rho u_{ref}^2 A$ and the **normalized yaw moment** $M_y^* = M_y/\rho u_{ref}^2 A D$ at $\lambda_{TI} = 6.0$ for a $\gamma_{TI} = 30^\circ$ yawed model wind turbine.

NOTES:

- Power P is the power extracted from the wind
 - Thrust T is the force acting on the rotor plane in the direction of the wind
 - A is the rotor swept area ($A = \pi D^2/4$)
 - The forces acting on the tower and the nacelle are included in C_T
2. The normalized **streamwise** (x-direction, main flow direction) **mean velocity** $u^* = u/u_{ref}$ in the wake $x/D=3$ and $x/D=6$ behind the rotor. The velocities should be extracted in a grid of a total of 357 measurement points ranging from $y/D=-1.60$ to $y/D=+1.60$ and $z/D=-2.00$ to $z/D=+2.00$. The distance between the single mesh points is $\Delta y/D = \Delta z/D = 0.10$. For a sketch of the measurement grid and a reference coordinate system, see *Figure 16*.
 3. The normalized **spanwise** (y-direction, upwards positive) **mean velocity** $v^* = v/u_{ref}$ in the wake $x/D=3$ and $x/D=6$ behind the rotor. The velocities should be extracted in the same grid of a total of 357 measurement points.
 4. The normalized **turbulent kinetic energy** $k^* = k/u_{ref}^2$ in the same grid of 357 points in the wake $x/D=3$ and $x/D=6$ behind the rotor. The turbulent kinetic energy is defined as $k = 1/2(u'^2 + v'^2 + w'^2)$ in a Cartesian coordinate system. Corresponding approximations can also be used.

Figure 16: Measurement grid (normalized with $R=0.5D$) in the wake behind the rotor. The grid consists of 357 measurement points, ranging from $y/D=-1.60$ to $y/D=+1.60$ in height and $z/D=-2.00$ to $z/D=+2.00$ in width. The normalized distance between the single grid points is $\Delta y/D = \Delta z/D = 0.10$

Test case 2

1. The **power coefficient** $C_{P,T1} = 2P/\rho u_{ref}^3 A$ and the **thrust coefficient** $C_{T,T1} = 2T/\rho u_{ref}^2 A$ and the normalized **yaw moment** $M_y^* = M_y/\rho u_{ref}^2 A D$ at $\lambda_{T1} = 6.0$ and $\gamma_{T1} = 30^\circ$ for the **upstream turbine LARS1**.

NOTES:

- The forces and moments acting on the tower and the nacelle are included in C_T and M_y^*
 - A positive yaw moment is defined in counter-clockwise direction around the positive y-axis (right hand rule)
 - The reference point for the yaw moment defined to be in the center of the rotor (not the tower).
2. The **power coefficient** $C_{P,T2} = 2P/\rho u_{ref}^3 A$ and the **thrust coefficient** $C_{T,T2} = 2T/\rho u_{ref}^2 A$ and the normalized **yaw moment** $M_y^* = M_y/\rho u_{ref}^2 A D$ at $\lambda_{T2} = 5.0$ and $\gamma_{T2} = 0^\circ$ for the **downstream turbine T2**.
 3. The normalized **streamwise** (x-direction, main flow direction) **mean velocity** $u^* = u/u_{ref}$ in the wake $x/D=3$ behind the second rotor (T2). The velocities should be extracted in the same grid as for test cases 1 and 3.
 4. The normalized **spanwise** (y-direction, upwards positive) **mean velocity** $v^* = v/u_{ref}$ in the wake $x/D=3$ behind the second rotor. The velocities should be extracted in the same grid as defined above.
 5. The normalized **turbulent kinetic energy** $k^* = k/u_{ref}^2$ in the same grid of 357 points in the wake $x/D=3$ behind the second rotor.

Description of computational method

Furthermore, the participants are kindly asked to provide a detailed description of the computational method they are using. A brief document should include all required information about:

- The name and type of the numerical code or software
- The turbulence model used (if applicable)
- The method of rotor modelling used (fully resolved rotor, blade element momentum, actuator disc method, actuator line method, ...)
- The parameters describing the computational mesh (resolution, number of cells/nodes, frame of reference, ...)
- The method of modelling the initial condition to the computational domain, i.e. the inflow conditions (resolved turbulence grid, velocity functions, ...)
- The source for the lift and drag coefficients for modelling forces on the rotor (if applicable)
- The structures and boundaries that have been included in the computational domain (wind tunnel walls, turbine towers and nacelles, ...)

References

- [1] Krogstad P.-Å., Eriksen P.E.; *"Blind test" calculations of the performance and wake development for a model wind turbine*. Renewable Energy. vol. 50, 2013
- [2] Pierella F., Krogstad P.-Å., Sætran L.R.; *Blind Test 2 calculations for two in-line model wind turbines where the downstream turbine operates at various rotational speeds*. Renewable Energy. vol. 70., 2014
- [3] Krogstad P.-Å., Sætran L.R., Adaramola M.S.; *"Blind Test 3" calculations of the performance and wake development behind two in-line and offset model wind turbines*. Journal of Fluids and Structures. vol. 52., 2014
- [4] Bartl, J., Sætran, L.R.; *Blind test comparison of the performance and wake flow between model wind turbines exposed to different turbulent inflow conditions*. Wind Energ. Sci. vol. 2, pp.55-76, 2017.
- [5] Medici, D., Alfredsson, P.H.; *Measurements on a Wind Turbine Wake: 3D Effects and Bluff Body Vortex Shedding*. Wind Energ. 2006; 9:219–236
- [6] Krogstad, P.-Å., Adaramola, M.S.; *Performance and near wake measurements of a model horizontal axis wind turbine*. Wind Energy, Vol. 15(5): pp. 743-756, 2012
- [7] Bastankhah, M., Porte-Agel, F.; *A wind-tunnel investigation of wind-turbine wakes in yawed conditions*. Wake Conference 2015, Journal of Physics: Conference Series Vol. 625 012014, 2015
- [8] Howland, M.F., Bossuyt, J., Martinez-Tossas, L.A., Meyers, J., and Meneveau, C.; *Wake structure in actuator disk models of wind turbines in yaw under uniform inflow conditions*. J. Renewable Sustainable Energy 8, 043301, 2016.
- [9] Fleming, P., Gebraad, P.M.O., Lee, S. van Wingerden, J.-W., Johnson, K., Churchfield, M., Michalakes, J., Spalart, P., Moriaty, P.; *Evaluating techniques for redirecting turbine wakes using SOWFA*. Renewable Energy Vol. 70 pp.211-218, 2014.
- [10] Vollmer, L., Steinfeld, G., Heinemann, D., Kühn, M. *Estimating the wake deflection downstream of a wind turbine in different atmospheric stabilities: an LES study*. Wind Energ. Sci., Vol.1, pp. 129–141, 2016.
- [11] Schottler, J., Hölling, A., Peinke, J., Hölling, M. *Wind tunnel tests on controllable model wind turbines in yaw*. 34th Wind Energy Symposium, AIAA SciTech Forum, AIAA 2016-1523, 2016.
- [12] Somers D.M.; *The S825 and S826 Airfoils*. National Renewable Energy Laboratory; NREL/SR-500-36344, 2005
- [13] Hsu, S.A., Meindl, E.A., and Gilhousen, D.B.: *Determining the power-law wind-profile exponent under near-neutral stability conditions at sea*, Journal of Applied Meteorology, 33(6), 757-765, 1994.
- [14] Krogstad P.-Å., Davidson P.A.; *Is grid turbulence Saffman turbulence?* J. Fluid Mech. 642, 2010.
- [15] Drela M.; *XFOIL Subsonic Airfoil Development System*; available at: <http://web.mit.edu/drela/Public/web/xfoil/> [accessed on 20.01.2017]
- [16] Sarmast S., Mikkelsen R.F.; *The experimental results of the NREL S826 Airfoil at low Reynolds numbers* DTU, Lyngby, Denmark, 2013
- [17] Ostovan, Y., Amiri, H., and Uzol, O.: *Aerodynamic Characterization of NREL S826 Airfoil at Low Reynolds Numbers*, RUZGEM Conference on Wind Energy Science and Technology, METU Ankara Campus, 2013.
- [18] Sagmo, K.F., Bartl, J., and Sætran, L.: *Numerical simulations of the NREL S826 airfoil*, Journal of Physics: Conference Series 753 082036, doi:10.1088/1742-6596/753/8/082036, 2016.
- [19] Selig, M.S., Guglielmo, J.J., Broeren, A.P., and Giguere, P.: *Summary of Low-Speed Airfoil Data; Vol.1* SoarTech Publications Virginia Beach, Virginia; ISBN 0-9646747-1-8, 1995. Available at http://m-selig.ae.illinois.edu/uiuc_lsat/Low-Speed-Airfoil-Data-VI.pdf [accessed on 7.2.2017]

Appendix

A. Technical drawings of the turbine geometry

A.1 NTNU model turbine LARS1

Figure A.1: Geometry details of NTNU model wind turbine LARS1

A.2 NTNU model turbine T2

Figure A.2: Geometry details of NTNU model wind turbine T2

A.3 ForWind model turbine

Figure A.3: Geometry details of ForWind model wind turbine

B. Airfoil geometry

B.1 NTNU blade: NREL S826 airfoil

x/c	y/c (upper surface, suction side)	x/c	y/c (lower surface, pressure side)
0.00000	0.0000	0.00000	0.00000
0.00018	0.001590	0.00021	-0.001460
0.00255	0.007480	0.00093	-0.002740
0.00954	0.016380	0.00216	-0.004030
0.02088	0.025960	0.00367	-0.005250
0.03651	0.035800	0.01367	-0.010350
0.05636	0.045620	0.02920	-0.015180
0.08026	0.055190	0.04998	-0.019600
0.10801	0.064340	0.07580	-0.023620
0.13934	0.072880	0.10637	-0.027290
0.17395	0.080680	0.14133	-0.030910
0.21146	0.087580	0.17965	-0.034860
0.25149	0.093430	0.21987	-0.038550
0.29361	0.098070	0.26153	-0.040640
0.33736	0.101330	0.30497	-0.040510
0.38228	0.102940	0.35027	-0.037940
0.42820	0.102490	0.39779	-0.032800
0.47526	0.100050	0.44785	-0.025630
0.52324	0.096070	0.50032	-0.017200
0.57161	0.090940	0.55484	-0.008410
0.61980	0.084890	0.61055	-0.000150
0.66724	0.078160	0.66644	0.006990
0.71333	0.070950	0.72142	0.012540
0.75749	0.063410	0.77434	0.016210
0.79915	0.055720	0.82409	0.017840
0.83778	0.047980	0.86953	0.017410
0.87287	0.040290	0.90945	0.014980
0.90391	0.032620	0.94257	0.011130
0.93072	0.024790	0.96813	0.006890
0.95355	0.016950	0.98604	0.003240
0.97251	0.009820	0.99655	0.000840
0.98719	0.004310	1.00000	0.000000
0.99668	0.001030		
1.00000	0.000000		

Table B.1: Coordinates of the NREL S826 airfoil

B.2 ForWind blade SD7003 airfoil

x/c	y/c (upper surface, suction side)	x/c	y/c (lower surface, pressure side)
0.00127	0.00438	0.00025	-0.00186
0.00697	0.01172	0.00457	-0.00741
0.01702	0.01932	0.01408	-0.01285
0.03130	0.02677	0.02839	-0.01759
0.04978	0.03372	0.04763	-0.02141
0.07244	0.03993	0.07182	-0.02438
0.09921	0.04526	0.10073	-0.02660
0.12993	0.04961	0.13407	-0.02809
0.16442	0.05292	0.17150	-0.02888
0.20240	0.05518	0.21268	-0.02900
0.24358	0.05639	0.25719	-0.02852
0.28760	0.05658	0.30456	-0.02752
0.33405	0.05581	0.35426	-0.02608
0.38250	0.05415	0.40572	-0.02428
0.43249	0.05171	0.45837	-0.02217
0.48350	0.04859	0.51161	-0.01980
0.53499	0.04494	0.56484	-0.01723
0.58641	0.04086	0.61748	-0.01450
0.63717	0.03649	0.66898	-0.01167
0.68673	0.03197	0.71883	-0.00887
0.73449	0.02744	0.76644	-0.00628
0.77985	0.02304	0.81118	-0.00403
0.82224	0.01884	0.85241	-0.00220
0.86112	0.01494	0.88957	-0.00082
0.89600	0.01139	0.92210	0.00008
0.92639	0.00824	0.94952	0.00052
0.95193	0.00547	0.97134	0.00057
0.97235	0.00310	0.98718	0.00037
0.98745	0.00132	0.99679	0.00011
0.99681	0.00031	1.00001	0.00000
1.00000	0.00000		

Table B.2: Coordinates of the SD7003-085-88 airfoil

C Blade geometry: chord and twist distribution

C.1. NTNU blade

Blade element No.	Radius r [m]	Chord c [m]	Twist angle φ [°]
1	0.0075000	0.013500	120.00
2	0.022500	0.013500	120.00
3	0.049000	0.013500	120.00
4	0.055000	0.049500	38.000
5	0.067500	0.081433	37.055
6	0.082500	0.080111	32.544
7	0.097500	0.077012	28.677
8	0.11250	0.073126	25.262
9	0.12750	0.069008	22.430
10	0.14250	0.064952	19.988
11	0.15750	0.061102	18.034
12	0.17250	0.057520	16.349
13	0.18750	0.054223	14.663
14	0.20250	0.051204	13.067
15	0.21750	0.048447	11.829
16	0.23250	0.045931	10.753
17	0.24750	0.043632	9.8177
18	0.26250	0.041529	8.8827
19	0.27750	0.039601	7.9877
20	0.29250	0.037831	7.2527
21	0.30750	0.036201	6.5650
22	0.32250	0.034697	5.9187
23	0.33750	0.033306	5.3045
24	0.35250	0.032017	4.7185
25	0.36750	0.030819	4.1316
26	0.38250	0.029704	3.5439
27	0.39750	0.028664	2.9433
28	0.41250	0.027691	2.2185
29	0.42750	0.026780	1.0970
30	0.44250	0.025926	-0.7167

Table C.1: NTNU blade chord length and twist angle distribution as function of the blade radius.

C.2. ForWind blade

Blade element No.	Radius r [m]	Chord c [m]	Twist angle φ [°]
1	0.000	0.051237	20.15
2	0.010	0.068684	16.74
3	0.020	0.069535	14.91
4	0.030	0.067229	12.97
5	0.040	0.064467	11.14
6	0.050	0.061566	9.48
7	0.060	0.058754	8.06
8	0.070	0.056038	6.79
9	0.080	0.053463	5.62
10	0.090	0.051065	4.69
11	0.100	0.048856	3.78
12	0.110	0.046825	3.00
13	0.120	0.044961	2.38
14	0.130	0.043221	1.79
15	0.140	0.041595	1.26
16	0.150	0.040043	0.79
17	0.160	0.038515	0.39
18	0.170	0.036963	0.04
19	0.180	0.035323	-0.29
20	0.190	0.033457	-0.57
21	0.200	0.031212	-0.82
22	0.210	0.028320	-1.03
23	0.220	0.024335	-1.34
24	0.230	0.018216	-1.60
25	0.240	0.003876	-1.79

Table C.2: ForWind blade chord length and twist angle distribution as function of the blade radius

D Airfoil performance data

D.1 NREL S826 airfoil

α	C_L	C_D	C_L/C_D	α	C_L	C_D	C_L/C_D
-40.0	-0.96710	0.39968	-2.4197	3.00	0.82540	0.023250	35.501
-35.0	-0.87580	0.36549	-2.3962	4.00	0.91800	0.024420	37.592
-30.0	-0.75170	0.32383	-2.3213	5.00	1.0019	0.025880	38.713
-25.0	-0.60080	0.27557	-2.1802	6.00	1.0783	0.027800	38.788
-20.0	-0.43470	0.22170	-1.9608	7.00	1.1469	0.030290	37.864
-18.0	-0.36800	0.19869	-1.8521	8.00	1.2060	0.033540	35.957
-16.0	-0.30430	0.17474	-1.7414	9.00	1.2550	0.037850	33.157
-14.0	-0.24910	0.14843	-1.6782	10.0	1.2929	0.043660	29.613
-12.0	-0.20180	0.12244	-1.6482	11.0	1.3320	0.049960	26.661
-11.0	-0.18650	0.10792	-1.7281	12.0	1.3509	0.059220	22.812
-10.0	-0.18110	0.091970	-1.9691	13.0	1.3718	0.069050	19.867
-9.00	-0.19240	0.073190	-2.6288	14.0	1.3784	0.081720	16.867
-8.00	-0.25200	0.054460	-4.6272	15.0	1.3638	0.098800	13.804
-7.00	-0.23440	0.038600	-6.0725	16.0	1.3431	0.11883	11.303
-6.00	-0.14360	0.029050	-4.9432	18.0	1.2563	0.17904	7.0169
-5.00	-0.049500	0.023940	-2.0677	20.0	1.1940	0.26157	4.5647
-4.00	0.071400	0.021820	3.2722	22.0	1.2493	0.29458	4.2410
-3.00	0.18800	0.021090	8.9142	25.0	1.3379	0.33390	4.0069
-2.00	0.30260	0.020730	14.597	30.0	1.4702	0.38800	3.7892
-1.00	0.41360	0.020770	19.913	34.0	1.5519	0.42331	3.6661
0.00	0.52200	0.021040	24.810	40.0	0.96620	0.63129	1.5305
1.00	0.62690	0.021530	29.118	50.0	0.84970	0.73405	1.1576
2.00	0.72880	0.022220	32.799				

Table D.1: Lift and drag coefficients of the S826 airfoil calculated for $Re=1.0 \cdot 10^5$ using XFOil

D.2 SD7003 airfoil

α	C_L	C_D	C_L/C_D	α	C_L	C_D	C_L/C_D
-8.25	-0.4952	0.10034	-4.93522	1.25	0.1671	0.01954	8.551689
-8.00	-0.4923	0.09715	-5.06742	1.50	0.2442	0.02031	12.02363
-7.75	-0.4895	0.09396	-5.20966	1.75	0.3133	0.02063	15.18662
-7.25	-0.4816	0.08744	-5.50778	2.00	0.3804	0.02063	18.43917
-7.00	-0.4743	0.08438	-5.62100	2.25	0.4344	0.02049	21.20059
-6.75	-0.4777	0.08177	-5.84200	2.50	0.4767	0.02037	23.40206
-6.50	-0.4618	0.07787	-5.93040	2.75	0.5058	0.02051	24.66114
-6.25	-0.4576	0.07472	-6.12420	3.00	0.5329	0.02067	25.78133
-6.00	-0.5038	0.04834	-10.4220	3.25	0.5585	0.02086	26.77373
-5.75	-0.4874	0.04356	-11.1892	3.50	0.5814	0.02125	27.36000
-5.50	-0.4683	0.03918	-11.9525	3.75	0.6048	0.02164	27.94824
-5.25	-0.4472	0.03586	-12.4707	4.00	0.6284	0.02205	28.49887
-5.00	-0.4242	0.03291	-12.8897	4.25	0.6514	0.0226	28.82301
-4.75	-0.4011	0.03035	-13.2158	4.50	0.6745	0.02322	29.04823
-4.50	-0.3774	0.02822	-13.3735	4.75	0.6979	0.02388	29.22529
-4.25	-0.3528	0.02623	-13.4502	5.00	0.7213	0.0246	29.32114
-4.00	-0.3287	0.02449	-13.4218	5.25	0.7447	0.02542	29.29583
-3.75	-0.3046	0.02301	-13.2377	5.50	0.7680	0.02633	29.16825
-3.50	-0.2806	0.02155	-13.0209	5.75	0.7910	0.02734	28.93197
-3.25	-0.2573	0.0202	-12.7376	6.00	0.8141	0.02847	28.59501
-3.00	-0.2359	0.01867	-12.6352	6.25	0.8379	0.02951	28.39376
-2.75	-0.2221	0.01715	-12.9504	6.50	0.8595	0.03099	27.73475
-2.50	-0.2185	0.01642	-13.3069	6.75	0.8824	0.03229	27.32735
-2.25	-0.1949	0.01612	-12.0906	7.00	0.9030	0.03408	26.49648
-2.00	-0.0848	0.0157	-5.40127	7.25	0.9254	0.03549	26.07495
-1.75	-0.0821	0.01541	-5.32771	7.50	0.9467	0.03745	25.27904
-1.50	-0.0722	0.01529	-4.72204	7.75	0.9634	0.03974	24.24258
-1.25	-0.0572	0.01527	-3.74591	8.00	0.9808	0.04233	23.17033
-1.00	-0.0401	0.01533	-2.61579	8.25	0.9960	0.04487	22.19746
-0.75	-0.0222	0.01545	-1.43689	8.50	1.0125	0.04763	21.25761
-0.50	0.0040	0.01564	-0.25575	8.75	1.0285	0.05015	20.50847
-0.25	0.0139	0.01589	0.87476	9.00	1.0200	0.0559	18.24687
0.00	0.0315	0.01621	1.94324	9.25	1.0360	0.05852	17.70335
0.25	0.0487	0.01661	2.93196	9.50	1.0184	0.06484	15.70635
0.50	0.0652	0.01711	3.81063	9.75	0.9971	0.07137	13.97086
0.75	0.0812	0.01769	4.59016	10.00	0.9750	0.07792	12.51283
1.00	0.0965	0.01838	5.25027	10.25	0.9540	0.08433	11.31270

Table D.2: Lift and drag coefficients of the SD7003-085-88 airfoil calculated for $Re=0.5 \cdot 10^5$ using XFOil ($N_{crit}=9$)

α	C_L	C_D	C_L/C_D	α	C_L	C_D	C_L/C_D
-9.00	-0.5197	0.10154	-5.11818	2.00	0.424	0.01218	34.81117
-8.75	-0.54	0.09832	-5.49227	2.25	0.4478	0.01239	36.14205
-8.50	-0.5614	0.09446	-5.94326	2.50	0.4718	0.01263	37.3555
-8.25	-0.5197	0.09015	-5.76484	2.75	0.4959	0.01289	38.47168
-8.00	-0.5203	0.08668	-6.00254	3.00	0.5202	0.01318	39.46889
-7.75	-0.563	0.08141	-6.91561	3.25	0.5446	0.0135	40.34074
-7.50	-0.535	0.07783	-6.87396	3.50	0.569	0.01384	41.11272
-7.25	-0.5256	0.07454	-7.05125	3.75	0.5935	0.0142	41.79577
-7.00	-0.5374	0.0683	-7.86823	4.00	0.618	0.0146	42.32877
-6.75	-0.5468	0.04834	-11.3115	4.25	0.6425	0.01503	42.74784
-6.50	-0.534	0.04258	-12.5411	4.50	0.6669	0.0155	43.02581
-6.25	-0.5205	0.03708	-14.0372	4.75	0.6914	0.01599	43.23952
-6.00	-0.5023	0.03347	-15.0075	5.00	0.7158	0.01652	43.3293
-5.75	-0.482	0.02998	-16.0774	5.25	0.7401	0.0171	43.2807
-5.50	-0.4605	0.02681	-17.1764	5.50	0.7644	0.01772	43.1377
-5.25	-0.4378	0.02525	-17.3386	5.75	0.7886	0.01838	42.90533
-5.00	-0.4141	0.02305	-17.9653	6.00	0.8127	0.01907	42.61668
-4.75	-0.39	0.02176	-17.9228	6.25	0.8367	0.01984	42.17238
-4.50	-0.3664	0.02028	-18.0671	6.50	0.8605	0.02063	41.7111
-4.25	-0.3424	0.01896	-18.0591	6.75	0.8842	0.02147	41.18305
-4.00	-0.3185	0.01793	-17.7635	7.00	0.9078	0.02241	40.5087
-3.75	-0.2946	0.017	-17.3294	7.25	0.9311	0.02344	39.7227
-3.50	-0.2716	0.01599	-16.9856	7.50	0.9539	0.0245	38.93469
-3.25	-0.2486	0.01512	-16.4418	7.75	0.9761	0.0256	38.12891
-3.00	-0.2263	0.01412	-16.0269	8.00	0.9978	0.02676	37.287
-2.75	-0.2053	0.01298	-15.8166	8.25	1.0187	0.02802	36.35617
-2.50	-0.1869	0.01207	-15.4847	8.50	1.0391	0.02943	35.30751
-2.25	-0.1718	0.01163	-14.7721	8.75	1.0589	0.03101	34.14705
-2.00	-0.159	0.01144	-13.8986	9.00	1.0786	0.03268	33.0049
-1.75	-0.1456	0.01133	-12.8508	9.25	1.0953	0.03505	31.24964
-1.50	-0.0785	0.0112	-7.00893	9.50	1.1144	0.03736	29.82869
-1.25	-0.0657	0.01122	-5.85561	9.75	1.1253	0.04051	27.77833
-1.00	-0.0485	0.01134	-4.2769	10.00	1.1349	0.04371	25.96431
-0.75	-0.0307	0.01155	-2.65801	10.25	1.1479	0.04599	24.95977
-0.50	-0.0037	0.01186	-0.31197	10.50	1.1546	0.05001	23.08738
-0.25	0.0572	0.01217	4.700082	10.75	1.1483	0.0539	21.30427
0.00	0.1155	0.01231	9.382616	11.00	1.1363	0.05826	19.50395
0.25	0.1754	0.01229	14.27177	11.25	1.118	0.06251	17.88514
0.50	0.2321	0.01215	19.10288	11.50	1.0958	0.06684	16.39437
0.75	0.2775	0.012	23.125	11.75	1.0727	0.07197	14.90482
1.00	0.3164	0.01189	26.6106	12.00	1.0484	0.07822	13.40322
1.25	0.348	0.01185	29.36709	12.25	1.0257	0.08552	11.99369
1.50	0.375	0.0119	31.51261	12.50	0.8646	0.13346	6.478346
1.75	0.3999	0.01201	33.29725	12.75	0.8815	0.13549	6.506015

Table D.3: Lift and drag coefficients of the SD7003-085-88 airfoil calculated for $Re=1.0 \cdot 10^5$ using XFOil ($N_{crit}=9$)